

Thermodynamics of Transfer of Hydrogen Ion from Water to Dioxane-Water Mixtures

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Manuscript received 29 January 1993

The thermodynamic dissociation constants for the isoelectric reaction $LH^+ \rightleftharpoons L + H^+$ (where L = 1,10-phenanthroline) have been determined pH-metrically and spectrophotometrically in dioxane + water (D + H₂O) mixtures (0–90 wt% of dioxane). The data were utilised to calculate the free energies of transfer of H⁺ ion from water to dioxane+water mixtures. Enthalpies and entropies of transfer of H⁺ ion (in 0–60 wt% of D) have also been determined using the calorimetric data of earlier experiments in a similar way. The changes in the p*K* values and the thermodynamics of transfer of H⁺ ion have been interpreted in terms of solvent basicity and ion-solvent interactions. The thermodynamics of transfer of H⁺ ion suggests that D + H₂O mixtures are more basic than water. The basicity increases and passes through a maximum in the region 45–50 wt% of D and ultimately above 80 wt% of D (D : H₂O ~ : 1); the binary mixtures are less basic than water. It appears that D is less basic than water in the liquid state. The results are consistent with the structural changes associated with the addition of a solvent D to water.

The addition of an organic solvent to water brings about a sharp change in the solvation of ions. The peculiarities of the aquo-organic mixtures are well reflected in the dramatic changes in the reaction rates¹⁻³ and medium effect ($\log_m Y_i$ or free energies of transfer $\Delta G_f^\ddagger(i)$ [$\log_m Y_i = \Delta G_f^\ddagger(i)/2.303 RT$] of ions which cannot be explained only on the basis of the change in the dielectric constants of the solvent mixtures. Moreover, the determination of single ion properties is a contentious subject as the values of single ion parameters obviously depend on the nature of extrathermodynamic assumptions and inherent limitations involved therein⁴⁻⁷. Nevertheless, the knowledge of the free energy of transfer of ions is needed to establish a 'Universal Scale' of activity, acidity and electrode potential.

The free energy of transfer of H⁺ ion in different mixed solvents is regarded to be the best method for determining the basicity of the solvent mixtures. It is, therefore, advisable to determine the free energy of transfer of ions using different methods and arrive at a consistent set of results.

With these objects in view, Lahiri and co-workers⁸⁻¹² developed a simple method of calculation of the free energy of transfer of H⁺ ion from water to aquo-organic mixtures based on the determination of the dissociation constants for the 'isoelectric' reaction,

(where L = 1,10-phenanthroline or 2,2'-bipyridine) in different solvent mixtures. The studies on the dissociation constants for reaction (1) have been extended to dioxane + water mixtures having a wide range of dielectric constants and the data have been utilised to calculate the free energies of transfer of H⁺ ion from water to dioxane + water mixtures.

We have also utilised the enthalpy values for reaction (1) previously determined¹³ to calculate the enthalpy of transfer of H⁺ ions. These data are coupled with the free energy of transfer of H⁺ ion to derive entropy values [$\Delta S_f^\ddagger(H^+)$].

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Results and Discussion

The thermodynamic dissociation constant (K) for the reaction (1) in aqueous or dioxane-water media can be written as

$$K = \frac{C_L \times C_H}{C_{LH}} \times \frac{f_L \times f_H}{f_{LH}} \quad (2)$$

where the C and f terms refer to the concentrations and activity coefficients in the respective solvent systems.

At low ionic strengths, the activity coefficients of the ion can be calculated accurately using Debye-Hückel equation,

$$-\log f_{\pm} = \frac{Az+z\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + a^o B\sqrt{\mu}} \quad (3)$$

The activity coefficient values are dependent on ion-size parameter (a^o). However, the values of the ion-size parameters are not known with certainty and a^o values for LH^+ and H^+ are definitely different. Thus the values of the activity coefficients f_H^+ and f_{LH^+} may be expected to differ but the difference must be small. The variation of f_L with ionic strengths and solvent composition is not known with certainty but the variation, if any, must be small at low ionic strengths in the respective solvent systems. The change in ionic strengths changes f_H^+ and f_{LH^+} values simultaneously. Thus $(f_L \times f_H^+)/f_{LH^+}$ term is assumed to be unity at low ionic strengths [(1.5–3.5

$\times 10^{-3} M$) in pH metric method and even less in spectrophotometric method] in the respective standard states.

Addition of inert electrolytes which may effectively change the 'medium effect' of ions, is avoided due to reasons described before^{7,8}.

The pK values of 1,10-phenanthroline have been calculated in the way described in our previous communications⁷⁻¹¹.

The free-energy of transfer $\Delta G_t^o(1)$ for the ionisation of LH^+ from water to mixed solvents have been calculated using the relation,

$$\Delta G_t^o(1) = 2.303 RT [pK_s(1) - pK_w(1)] \quad (4)$$

where $K_s(1)$ and $K_w(1)$ represent the dissociation constants for the reaction (1) in mixed solvents (S) and water (W).

The average values of pK for 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) determined pH-metrically and spectrophotometrically are recorded in Table 1. We have also recorded the pK values for 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) from literature¹⁴.

The pK values when plotted against $1/\epsilon$ (ϵ being the dielectric constant or relative permittivity of the solvent mixture) and mole-fraction of dioxane, show linearity at low percentage of dioxane (Fig. 1), but at high percentages considerable deviation arises.

TABLE I - DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS AND ENTHALPY FOR THE REACTION $LH^+ \rightleftharpoons L + H^+$ IN DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURE AND OTHER PROPERTIES AT 298 K

Dioxane wt%	pK values for 1,10-phenanthroline			$-\Delta H^o$ (Phen) kJ mol ⁻¹	pK values for 2,2'-bipyridine, pH-metric	$-\Delta G_t^o(1)$ (KJ mol ⁻¹)	
	pH-metric	Spectrophotometric	Average			Bipyridine	Phenanthroline
0		5.05	5.05	16.74 (17.03)	4.47		
10	4.75 (+0.02)	4.80	4.78	18.66	4.25	1.26	1.54
20	4.64 (+0.03)	4.64	4.64	19.79	4.08	2.23	2.34
30	4.53 (+0.03)	4.47	4.50	18.70	3.87	3.42	3.14
40	4.31 (+0.03)	4.37	4.34		3.71	4.34	4.06
45				14.52		4.78	4.73
50	4.09 (+0.05)	4.10	4.10		3.56	5.19	5.42
60	4.07 (+0.05)	3.96	4.02	14.64	3.41	6.05	5.88
70	3.78 (+0.05)	3.87	3.83		3.24	7.02	6.96
80	3.82 (+0.10)	3.85	3.84		3.21	7.19	6.90
90	-	4.36 (+0.2)	4.36		3.23	7.07	3.94

Fig. 1. Plots of pK for 1,10-phenanthroline : (A) against $1/\epsilon \times 10^2$ and (B) against mole fraction of dioxane $\times 10^2$.

The pK values of the ligands decrease and pass through minima at ~ 50 wt% of dioxane, similar to those observed in other solvent systems like ME (2-methoxyethanol) and DME (1,2-dimethoxyethane)^{7-11,15} etc. The appearance of such minima can be attributed to the changed solvational behaviour of the ligands and their conjugate acids in the solvent mixtures.

The capability of attachment of H^+ ion to the ligands or to the solvent is governed by the relative basicities of the ligands and solvent molecules. Thus, the increased dissociation of LH^+ definitely indicates the increased basicity of the solvent mixtures.

It is well known that the ion-solvent interactions and basicity of the solvent mixtures can be best determined from the free energy of transfer of H^+ ion [$\Delta G_{tr}^0(H^+)$] from water to mixed solvents.

Equation (5) for the reaction (1)^{7,8} can be written in terms of free energy of transfer of individual components,

$$\Delta G_{tr}^0(1) = \Delta G_{tr}^0(L) + \Delta G_{tr}^0(H^+) - \Delta G_{tr}^0(LH^+) \quad (5)$$

The free energy changes of single ions cannot be determined thermodynamically. The known extrathermodynamic assumption that the free energies of transfer of ion is composed of free energy

of transfer of 'neutral part' $\Delta G_{tr}^0(\text{neut})$ ^{16,17} and electrostatic part $\Delta G_{tr}^0(\text{el})$ has been utilised to determine the free energy of transfer of single ions. This means

$$\Delta G_{tr}^0(LH^+) = \Delta G_{tr}^0(L) + \Delta G_{tr(\text{el})}^0(LH^+) \quad (6)$$

Combining equations (5) and (6) and rearranging, we get,

$$\Delta G_{tr}^0(H^+) = \Delta G_{tr}^0(1) + \Delta G_{tr(\text{el})}^0(LH^+) \quad (7)$$

There is no absolutely correct equation to calculate $\Delta G_{tr}^0(\text{el})$ and every equation is defective in some respect or other and all the extrathermodynamic methods involve some assumptions with inherent limitations. Moreover, the true values of the radii of ions and the orientations of ions in solvent molecules will always be a matter of speculation. Therefore, in absence of suitable and reliable equation, we use the Born equation¹⁸ (eq. 8) for calculating $\Delta G_{tr(\text{el})}^0$. This is actually the energy change resulting from the differences in the free energies of transfer of a gaseous ion in a medium of unit relative permittivity to aquo-organic mixtures (relative permittivity ϵ_s), and water (relative permittivity ϵ_w),

$$\Delta G_{tr(\text{el})}^0(B) = \frac{Nz^2e^2}{2r_{LH^+}} \left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_s} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_w} \right) \quad (8)$$

where r_{LH^+} has been taken to be $3.78 \text{ \AA}^{7,8}$.

However, in calculating $\Delta G_{(el)}^0$, the energy of interactions arising not only from Born charging (B) but also energy due to ion-dipole (i-d), ion-induced-dipole (i-i-d), ion-quadrupole (i-q) interactions are taken into consideration^{19,20}. Thus

$$\Delta G_{(el)}^0 = \Delta G_{(el)(B)}^0 + \Delta G_{(i-d)}^0 + \Delta G_{(i-i-d)}^0 + \Delta G_{(i-q)}^0 \quad (9)$$

We have neglected $\Delta G_{(i-q)}^0$ due to lack of knowledge of quadrupole moment of dioxane and other weak interactions. The expressions²⁰ for the energy terms are

$$\Delta G_{(i-d)}^0 = - \frac{n N Z_i e \mu}{(r_i + r_s)^2} \quad (10)$$

and

$$\Delta G_{(i-i-d)}^0 = - \frac{n N \alpha (Z_i e)^2}{2 (r_i + r_s)^4} \quad (11)$$

where n , m , α and r_s are solvation number (assumed to be unity), dipole moment, polarisability and radius of the solvent molecules respectively. The parameters are¹⁹ $\mu_w = 1.86 \text{ D}$, $\alpha_w = 1.47 \times 10^{-30} \text{ m}^3$; $r_w = 1.38 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$ for water and $\mu_D = 0.4 \text{ D}$, $\alpha_D = 8.67 \times 10^{-30} \text{ m}^3$; $r_D = 2.58 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}$ for dioxane.

The radius of aquo-organic mixtures are calculated using the relationship,

$$V_m = \frac{M_s}{d_s} = \frac{4}{3} \pi r_s^3 N \quad (12)$$

where V_m is the molar volume of the binary mixtures and M_s and d_s represent the mean molar mass and density (determined experimentally) respectively.

The values of $\Delta G_{(i-d)}^0$ and $\Delta G_{(i-i-d)}^0$ in aquo-organic mixtures have been calculated assuming the solute to be distributed in the solvents in the ratio of their mole fractions X_1 and X_2 . Thus,

$$\Delta G_{(i-d)}^0 = [X_1 \Delta G_{(i-d)(W)}^0 + X_2 \Delta G_{(i-d)(org.solv.)}^0] - \Delta G_{(i-d)(W)}^0 \dots \text{etc} \quad (13)$$

$\Delta G_{(i-d)W}^0$ or $\Delta G_{(i-d)(org.solv.)}^0$ is the free energy change in taking an ion (radius r_i) from water (radius r_w) or organic solvent (radius r_{org}) to a solvent of radius r_s .

In calculating $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(B)$, we prefer the use of the radius of bare ion similar to that used by Kim¹⁹ and it is reasonable to assume that different interactions take place only after the introduction of ion in the solvent. However, it may be argued that in view of solvation of ions the modified equation (14) should be used in calculating $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(B)$,

$$\Delta G_{(el)}^0(B) = \frac{N z^2 e^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{(r_{LH^+}^+ + r_s) \epsilon_s} - \frac{1}{(r_{LH^+}^+ + r_w) \epsilon_w} \right] \quad (14)$$

where r_s and r_w are the radii of the solvent and water respectively. The values $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(B)$, $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(\text{Total})$, i.e. $\Delta G_{(B+i-d+i-i-d)}^0$ assuming monosolvation, have been recorded in Table 2.

The modified $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(B)$ and $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(\text{Total})$ values using solvated radii are given in parenthesis. The $\Delta G_{(el)}^0$ values (which is the difference of $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(S)$ and $\Delta G_{(el)}^0(W)$ in mixed solvent S and water W respectively) based on one-layer solvation model²¹ are given. The equation is

$$\Delta G_{(el)}^0 = \frac{N z^2 e^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_1} - 1 \right] \left[\frac{1}{r_{LH^+}} - \frac{1}{b} \right] + \frac{N z^2 e^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon'} - 1 \right] \left\{ \frac{1}{b} \right\} \quad (15)$$

where $b = r_{LH^+} + r_s$, is the radius of the appropriate solvent, $\epsilon_1 = 2$ and ϵ' is the appropriate relative permittivity or bulk dielectric constant of the solvent in question.

Recently, Rashin and Honig²² derived an expression for $\Delta G_{(el)}^0$ of an ion between two solvents by considering the transference of the ion from the first solvent to vacuum and therefrom into the second solvent. The expression is

$$\Delta G_{(el)}^0 = \frac{N z^2 e^2}{2} \left[\left(\frac{1}{\epsilon_s r_{c_s}} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_w r_{c_w}} \right) + \left(\frac{1}{r_{c_w}} - \frac{1}{r_{c_s}} \right) \right] \quad (16)$$

where r_{c_s} and r_{c_w} are the cavity radii of the ion in the two solvents respectively. However, the cavity radii of the ion of PhenH^+ in the solvents cannot be determined. Instead of cavity radii, we have utilised the solvated radii of the ion assumed to be equivalent to the cavity radii of the ion in the respective solvents. The $\Delta G_{(el)}^0$ calculated in this way are also included in Table 2 for comparison. Obviously the contributions due to

TABLE 2— VALUES OF $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{B})$, $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{B}+\text{i-d}+\text{i-i-d})$, $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{ONE LAYER MODEL})$ AND USING EQUATION (15) FROM DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURES (kJ mol^{-1}), CONVERSION FACTOR (kJ mol^{-1}) AND EXCESS DIELECTRIC CONSTANT $\epsilon_r^E(x)$

Dioxane wt %	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{B})$	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{i-d})$	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{i-i-d})$	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{Total})$	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{one layer model})$	$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{Rashin and Honig's eqn. 17})$	$-\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)^{**}$			Conversion factor to get $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)(\text{N})$ from $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)(\text{C})$	Excess dielectric constant of mixing $\epsilon_r^E(x)$
							Bipy	Phen	Average		
10	0.30 (0.21)	0.53	-0.12	0.71 (0.62)	0.57	0.83	0.96 (0.55)	1.24 (0.83)	1.10 (0.69)	-0.18	-1.95
20	0.70 (0.48)	1.25	-0.29	1.66 (1.44)	1.24	1.87	1.53 (0.57)	1.64 (0.68)	1.59 (0.63)	-0.38	-2.39
30	1.23 (0.84)	2.02	-0.45	2.80 (2.41)	2.12	3.34	2.19 (0.62)	2.11 (0.54)	2.15 (0.58)	-0.61	-4.21
40	1.98 (1.35)	2.99	-0.63	4.34 (3.71)	3.27	5.10	2.36 (0.00)	2.07 (-0.29)	2.22 (-0.15)	-0.86	-5.43
45	2.49 (1.69)	3.54	-0.68	5.35 (4.55)	3.98		2.29 (-0.57)	2.24 (-0.62)	2.27 (-0.60)	-1.02	-6.06
50	3.09 (2.09)	4.15	-0.86	6.38 (5.38)	4.77	7.37	2.10 (-1.19)	2.33 (-0.96)	2.22 (-1.08)	-1.16	-6.54
60	4.87 (3.26)	5.67	-1.14	9.40 (7.79)	6.92	10.48	1.18 (-3.35)	1.01 (-3.52)	1.10 (-3.44)	-1.51	-7.88
70	8.21 (5.42)	7.53	-1.43	14.31 (11.52)	11.37	15.21	-1.19 (-7.29)	-1.25 (-7.35)	-1.22 (-7.32)	-1.91	-8.04
80	15.14 (9.78)	9.97	-1.78	23.33 (17.97)	16.42	23.00	-7.95 (-16.14)	-8.24 (-16.43)	-8.10 (-16.29)	-2.41	-8.10
90	31.13 (19.39)	13.28	-2.11	42.30 (30.56)	28.55		-24.06 (-35.23)	-27.19 (-38.36)	-25.63 (-36.80)	-3.02	-4.38

*Values in parenthesis are obtained using eqn. (14). **Values in parenthesis represent $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$ using $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{Total})$.

$\frac{Nz^2e^2}{2} \left[\frac{1}{r_{c_w}} - \frac{1}{r_{c_s}} \right]$ value become dominant. However, since the equation has not been utilised by most of the workers, it was not utilised to calculate $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$.

The uncertainties in $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0$ values using different equations can be ascertained from Table 2. The $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$ values [in molar units using $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{B})$ and $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{Total})$] in dioxane + water mixtures using bipy, phen and their averages are recorded in Table 2. The $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$ values based on modified $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{B})$ or $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{Total})$ can easily be calculated from Table 2. The average values are preferred as it takes into account the uncertainties that can occur in such calculations.

The 'conversion factor' to obtain the free energy of transfer of H^+ in mole fraction scale $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)_\text{N}$ from molar scale $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)_\text{C}$ is given by

$$\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)_\text{N} - \Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)_\text{C} \approx 2.30 RT \log \frac{M_w d_s}{d_w M_s} \quad (17)$$

Excellent consistency (both qualitative and quantitative) in $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$ values are obtained particularly when we consider the uncertainties to the extent of 0.5 kJ mol^{-1} which may arise from various extraneous factors like change in asymmetry potential, liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude and high resistance of the dioxane + water medium associated with the determination of pK values and other approximations involved in calculating $\Delta G_{i(\text{el})}^0(\text{H}^+)$.

The values of the free energies of transfer of ions from one solvent to another, however, do not give any information regarding structural contributions in view of the compensation of the $\Delta H_{i(\text{el})}^0$ and $T\Delta S_{i(\text{el})}^0$ terms which are likely to give better insight regarding structural contributions. We, therefore, utilised the $\Delta H_{i(\text{el})}^0$ data for $\text{PhenH}^+ \rightleftharpoons \text{Phen} +$

H⁺ system reported previously in dioxane + water mixtures at low percentages¹³ (upto 60 wt%) to calculate ΔH_f⁰(H⁺) in a similar way²³ reported earlier.

The enthalpy changes for reaction (1) in water and mixed solvents were determined by measuring calorimetrically the heat changes accompanying the complete conversion of Phen to PhenH⁺ from which ΔH_f⁰(neut) values of Phen were calculated.

ΔH_{f(ℓ)}⁰(LH⁺) has been calculated using the Born equation,

$$\Delta H_{f(\ell)}^0(\text{LH}^+) = \frac{Nz^2e^2}{2r} \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_M} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_w} \right] + \frac{Nz^2e^2}{2r} T \times \left[\frac{1}{\epsilon_M} \cdot \frac{d \ln \epsilon_M}{dT} - \frac{1}{\epsilon_w} \cdot \frac{d \ln \epsilon_w}{dT} \right] \quad (18)$$

The relative permittivities of solvents at different temperatures have been taken from the data of Akerlöf and Short²⁴.

Further improvements of the results are possible if we take into consideration of ΔH_{f(ℓ)}⁰(i-d), ΔH_{f(ℓ)}⁰(i-i-d) etc. The method is not surely free from defects but in view of isoelectric nature of the reactions, the effects due to ionic strengths and dielectric constants are eliminated to a large extent.

The ΔH_f⁰(H⁺) together with ΔG_f⁰(H⁺) are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 3 – THERMODYNAMICS OF TRANSFER OF H⁺ ION FROM WATER TO DIOXANE + WATER MIXTURES AT 298 K (IN kJ mol⁻¹)

Dioxane wt%	ΔH _{f(ℓ)} ⁰ *	ΔH _f ⁰ (H ⁺)*	ΔG _f ⁰ (H ⁺)*	TΔS _f ⁰ (H ⁺)
10	-0.32(+0.09)	-2.24(-1.83)	-1.10(-0.69)	-1.14
20	-0.71(0.25)	-3.76(-2.80)	-1.59(-0.63)	-2.17
30	-1.13(0.44)	-3.10(-1.53)	-2.05(-0.48)	-1.05
45	-2.77(0.59)	-0.05(+2.81)	-2.27(0.60)	2.22
60	-4.16(0.37)	-2.06(+2.47)	-1.10(3.44)	-0.96

*Values in parenthesis are based on ΔH_{f(ℓ)}⁰(Total) or ΔG_f⁰(ℓ) (Total).

Comparison of ΔH_f⁰(H⁺) or TΔS_f⁰(H⁺) is not possible due to lack of relevant data. However, the comparison of ΔG_f⁰(H⁺) values in mole-fraction scale is possible and is given in Table 4.

It is to be noted that the single ion values

are obtained using extrathermodynamic assumptions with inherent limitations and can never be absolute. The 'reference electrolyte' method using TATB has been adjudged to be the best method for the determination of single ion values by Kim¹⁹, Popovych^{4,6} and Marcus⁷. The single ion values of H⁺ ion are based on the difference in the solubility data of Ph₄AsPi, KPh₄, KPi and HPi. Naturally, the errors in these determinations are compounded in ΔG_f⁰(H⁺) values determined by the 'reference electrolyte' method.

TABLE 4 – VALUES OF ΔG_f⁰(H⁺) (kJ mol⁻¹, MOLE FRACTION SCALE)*

Dioxane wt%	Present work	Ref. 25	Ref. 26
10	1.3(0.9)	1.59	2.65
20	2.0(1.0)		5.2
30	2.8(1.2)	5.65	7.1
40	3.1(0.7)		8.3
45	3.3(0.4)		8.4
50	3.4(0.1)	4.32	8.1
60	2.6(-1.9)		6.7
70	0.7(-5.4)		4.1
80	-5.7(-13.9)		

*Value in parenthesis represent values using ΔG_{f(ℓ)}⁰(Total).

The method is based on the assumption of (i) no ion-pair formation or association (a probability which cannot be ruled out at high percentages of organic solvents), (ii) no micelle formation (highly probable in aqueous solution) and crystal solvate formation, and (iii) equal solvation of Ph₄As⁺ and BPh₄⁻ ions (though the nature of solvation Ph₄As⁺ and BPh₄⁻ are different).

The ions are probably not equally solvated in all solvents as TATB cannot be utilised for the determination of single ion equivalent conductance values in different solvents²⁷. Therefore, the method cannot be taken to be free from error. The solvent-sorting method of Wells²⁶ is applicable to water-rich media. The validity of the solvent-sorting equilibrium constant(K_c) for the reaction,

is questionable. The determination of K_c involves extrapolations to zero dilution resulting in uncer-

tainties. The assumption regarding the contribution due to $\Delta G_{(el)}$ is doubtful.

Like other methods, our method is based on extrathermodynamic assumptions which are open to criticism. But some of the advantages of our method are as follows. (i) The dissociation constant for the reaction (1) can be measured accurately in dilute solutions so that the dissociation constant determined can be regarded to be thermodynamic dissociation constant and the method gives directly the Gibbs energy changes of transfer for H^+ ions. (ii) It is known that $\gamma_i = m\gamma_i \cdot s\gamma_i$. We can eliminate $s\gamma_i$ effect by suitable equations or by suitable extrapolation. However, 'medium effect' changes with salt concentrations. Primary solvation also changes with concentration of electrolytes and there is no means to know the changes in the 'medium effect' with salt concentration. Thus, keeping the reaction conditions same throughout and working in dilute solutions, the 'medium effect' should be better ascertained.

Considering the limitations and assuming an uncertainty to the extent of 1 kJ in single ions, our results agree well with the values reported by Datta and Kundu²⁵ using TATB method (except at 30 wt%). The values reported by Wells²⁶ are considerably more negative. However, the $\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ values calculated on the basis of modified $\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ}(B)$ comes closer to Well's values. It is desirable to use different methods and derive reasonably consistent set of single ion values.

The increasingly negative $\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ in going from H_2O to $D + H_2O$ mixtures indicates that the binary mixtures are more basic than water. The basicity passes through a maximum in the region 45–50 wt% of D and ultimately above ~ 80 wt% of D ($D : H_2O = 1 : 1$), the binary mixtures are less basic than water.

The results suggest that D in the liquid state is less basic than H_2O similar to our observation in case of ME or DME¹⁵.

$\Delta H_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ and $T\Delta S_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ have been found to work in the opposite directions. $\Delta H_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ is endothermic initially but becomes exothermic above 45 wt%.

$T\Delta S_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$, which measures structural changes i.e. enhancement of breakdown of structure, indicates that the transfer process is favourable initially, but subsequently becomes unfavourable.

The results are closely related to structural changes in $D + H_2O$ mixtures. The variation of excess thermodynamic properties of mixing (i.e. ΔG^E , ΔH^E , ΔS^E) with composition of $D + H_2O$ mixtures (where enhancement of water-structure occurs with the addition of co-solvent) resembles more closely with those for acetone + water mixtures (where structural breakdown is observed)²⁶⁻³².

The structure-breaking character of D was inferred by Wells²⁶ from the very flat maximum in the viscosity-composition curves²⁸, weak peak in the ultrasonic absorption²⁹, absence of maximum in the Walden products in most cases³⁰ and particularly from the negative changes in the structural contribution to the temperature of maximum density³¹ (ΔT^h) as well as from the changes in the heats of solution of quaternary ammonium salts³² and argon³³ in $D + H_2O$ mixtures. However, better insight regarding the structural properties of $D + H_2O$ mixtures can be derived from the excess relative permittivities $\epsilon_r^E(x)$ of the solvent mixtures calculated using De-crooq's formula³⁴,

$$\epsilon_r^E(x) = \epsilon_r(x) - [(1 - \phi)\epsilon_w + \phi\epsilon_D] \quad (20)$$

where ϕ is the volume fraction of D . The plot of $\epsilon_r^E(x)$ (Table 2) vs wt% of D (Fig. 2) exhibits negative deviations from the ideal values. The curves show that in the water-rich region (upto 20 wt% of D), the deviations are relatively small which possibly indicate a competition between structure-formation and structural breakdown of water where the latter predominates resulting in overall structural breakdown. The sharp decrease in $\epsilon_r^E(x)$ in the region 20–60 wt% indicates structural breakdown and possible complex formation between D and H_2O . The region 60–80 wt% indicates D , $2H_2O$ complex formation zone, beyond which formation of pure D -structure occurs replacing D , $2H_2O$ structure. The results are akin to our observations based on $\Delta G_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$, $\Delta H_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$ and $T\Delta S_{(el)}^{\circ}(H^+)$.

Fig 2 Excess dielectric properties of dioxane + H₂O mixtures against wt% of dioxane

The addition of D having two O-centres with increased electron density causes the breakdown of the polymeric structure of water (cation-O-type interactions) leading to increase basicity which is maximum in the region of 45 wt% where ΔH^E is minimum. Due to cooperative H-bonding between D and H₂O, the basicity decreases with the formation of D, 2H₂O upto 70 wt% of D beyond which D, 2H₂O structure is gradually replaced by 2D.2H₂O and ultimately by D-structure with decrease in basicity. The decrease in entropy is usually associated with order.

However, preferential solvation of H⁺ ion may also be the reasons for the change in $\Delta G_f^{\circ}(H^+)$ and other thermodynamic properties. But nothing specific can be said about the preferential solvation of ions in absence of spectral evidences using nmr or ir spectral studies.

Experimental

Dioxane (E. Merck, B.D.H. or S.D.'s) was purified³⁵. The distilled solvent was utilised within 24 h. 1,10-Phenanthroline (G.R., E. Merck) was used as such.

Other experimental details are similar to those described in our earlier communications⁸⁻¹².

The solvent mixtures were prepared by weight and the density values were determined using a calibrated pycnometer. The dielectric constant values of the solvent mixtures were taken from the literature data²⁴.

The absorptivity readings were recorded with a Varian Techtron 634 spectrophotometer maintained at 298 K. The pH-meter readings were taken with a Systronic digital pH-meter having an accuracy of 0.01 pH unit. In the pH-metric method of determination of pK values, the meter-readings of a number of solutions of HClO₄ of varying concentrations ($1.5-3.5 \times 10^{-3} M$) were taken in presence and absence of the ligand. The difference of H⁺ ion concentrations obtained from the meter-readings of the corresponding solutions gave the amount of LH⁺ and the meter-reading with 'appropriate correction' gave the H⁺ ion concentration of the solution.

Calibration of glass electrode: The determination of the dissociation constants of acids requires accurate values of H⁺ ion concentrations. The glass-calomel electrode combination was utilised for this purpose. The glass electrode was calibrated in the way suggested by previous workers^{25,36-39}. Pal *et al.*³⁵ studied the behaviour of glass electrode in dioxane + water mixtures and found that the electrode behaves reversibly and the agreement between the results obtained by different group of workers are good upto 70 wt% of dioxane above which considerable deviations occur. Even the dissociation constant values of formic acid at 82% dioxane determined by previous workers⁴⁰ differ considerably.

The difference at higher percentages may be due to (i) association of HCl, HClO₄ and (ii) impurities in the solvent particularly due to peroxide formation in dioxane on keeping. Both the phenomena may cause appreciable changes in pH values and the changes appear to depend on time.

Dioxane from different sources was purified using the same procedure and the results of pH measurements differ particularly at higher percentages (~80%) and

are attributed to peroxide formation in dioxane in presence of dissolved oxygen. Precipitation of HClO_4 also takes place at 90 wt% of dioxane and beyond.

The reliability of the correction terms' and measurement of H^+ ions concentrations were checked by determining the meter-readings of five known concentrations of H^+ ion ($1.5\text{--}3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$). The 'correction term' $\log U_{\text{H}}$ was obtained from the relationship,

$$-\log [\text{H}^+] = B + \log U_{\text{H}} \quad (20)$$

where $[\text{H}^+]$ represents the stoichiometric $[\text{H}^+]$ ion concentration of the reference solution and B represents the meter-reading. Consistent $\log U_{\text{H}}$ values indicate the reliability of the results. The experiment was repeated at each percentage of dioxane + water mixtures.

However, as pointed out by Bates⁴¹, we also feel that the application of the 'correction terms' once determined may not constitute a procedure of highest accuracy. It is desirable that the 'correction terms' should be determined at the beginning and at the end of each set of measurements where better accuracy is desired.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (K.M.) wishes to thank the U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Teacher Fellowship in the F.I.P. Scheme.

References

1. A. J. PARKER, *Quart. Rev. (London)*, 1962, 163; *Chem. Rev.*, 1969, 69, 1.
2. D. W. WELLS in "Physical Chemistry of Organic Solvent System", eds. A. K. CONINGTON and T. DICKINSON, Plenum Press, London, 1973. Chap. 6.
3. M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS, B. CLARK, P. P. DUCE, A. W. HAKIN, N. GOSAL, S. RADULOVIC, P. GUARDADO, F. SANCHEZ, C. D. HUBBARD and E. A. ABU GHARIB, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1968, 82, 1471.
4. O. POPOVYCH and R. P. T. TOMKINS, "Nonaqueous Solution Chemistry", Wiley, New York, 1981. Chap. 5.
5. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1112.
6. O. POPOVYCH, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, 85, 4167.
7. Y. MARCUS, *Rev. Anal. Chem.*, 1980, 5, 53.
8. D. SENGUPTA, A. PAL and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 2685.
9. A. K. BHATTACHARYYA, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1984, 265, 372.
10. S. K. CHAKRAVARTY, D. SENGUPTA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1986, 267, 969.
11. C. C. DEB, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, 1984, 93, 421.
12. K. MAZUMDER (SENGUPTA), S. C. LAHIRI and D. C. MUKHERJEE, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1989, 142, 1.
13. S. C. LAHIRI, A. K. ROY and S. ADITYA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1976, 16, 277.
14. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 567.
15. S. K. GHOSH, D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1985, 147, 41.
16. C. L. DELIGNY and M. ALFENAAR, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1965, 84, 81.
17. M. ALFENAAR and C. L. DELIGNY, *Recl. Trav. Chim.*, 1967, 86, 929.
18. M. BORN, *Z. Phys.*, 1920, 1, 45.
19. J. KIM, *Z. Phys. Chem. (New Folge)*, 1978, 113, 129; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, 82, 191.
20. J. O.' M. P. BOCKRIS and A. K. N. REDDY, "Modern Electrochemistry", Plenum Press, New York, Vol. I, Chap. 2.
21. M. H. ABRAHAM and J. LISZI, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1980, 76, 1219.
22. A. A. RASHIN and B. HONIG, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1985, 89, 5588.
23. S. K. CHAKRAVARTY and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Therm. Anal.*, 1984, 29, 815.
24. G. AKERLÖF, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 4125; G. AKERLÖF and O. A. SHORT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1241.
25. J. DATTA and K. K. KUNDU, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1981, 59, 3149.
26. C. F. WELLS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1978, 74, 1569.
27. B. S. KRUMGALZ, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1983, 79, 571; 1985, 81, 247.
28. J. A. GEDDES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4832.
29. K. ARAKAWA and N. JAKENAKA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, 42, 5.
30. J. C. JUSTICE, R. BURY and C. TREINER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 56, 1708; R. L. KAY and T. L. BROADWATER, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1971, 16, 667.
31. G. WADA and S. UMEDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1962, 35, 1797.
32. R. K. MOHANTY and J. C. AHLUWALIA, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1972, 1, 1531.
33. A. BEN-NAIM and G. MORAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, 61, 821.
34. D. DECROOQ, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr., Part 1*, 1964, 127.
35. S. K. PAL, U. C. BHATTACHARYYA, S. C. LAHIRI and S.

- ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 497.
36. L. G. VAN UITERT and C. C. HAAS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 451.
37. H. M. N. H. IRVING and U. S. MANHOT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1215.
38. U. C. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Frankfurt)*, 1966, **50**, 131.
39. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 319.
40. H. S. HARNED and B. B. OWEN, "The Physical Chemistry of Electrolytic Solutions", 3rd. ed., Reinhold, New York, 1958.
41. R. G. BATES in "Solute Solvent Interactions", eds. J. F. COETZEE and C. D. RITCHIE, M. Dekker, New York, 1969, Chap. 2.